

CRYPTOGRAPHIC APPROACH TO ENHANCING COMPUTER-BASED TEST SECURITY: EXAMINATION NUMBER GENERATION AND AUTHENTICATION SCHEME

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decades, authors have created multiple question papers in Computer-Based Tests (CBT) by adopting Fisher-Yate's, Sattolo's and key-word based shuffling algorithms without indicating access procedure to the question papers. In this research, an Examination Number Generation and Authentication Scheme (ENGAS) is proposed which is a novel approach to CBT security that generates a large number of batches of examination numbers using asymmetric cryptographic schemes to provide secure and automated question Paper assembly. During design, cryptographic and complexity management algorithms were harnessed to determine the scheme's functionality and performance. Next, a high-level algorithm of the scheme was developed using Greedy, recursive and Divide-and-Conquer algorithm development approaches. Lastly, the developed algorithms were simulated and integrated to a CBT using ASP.NET Core, Entity Framework and SQL Server 2014. Coverage testing based on the required functionalities and security level determination indicated that ENGAS was well consolidated with leptokurtic cryptographic features distribution for secure question paper assembly, scalable to meet extreme population increase and capable of eliminating the use of proxy and question paper personalization.

Keywords: Scalable, LLeptokurtic, Asymmetric cryptographic scheme, Greedy algorithm development, Recursive algorithm development, Divide-and-conquer

INTRODUCTION

The purposes of an examination number during examination are to provide identification to candidates, guide the student to the assigned sit, provide a link to the question type and subsequently the result (Nitin *et al*, 2019). Conventional examination number generation systems usually combine year, center number and registration number to form examination numbers. This manual approach provides an effective means for student identification during Paper and Pen Test (PPT) (Papa *et al*, 2021). However, with the evolution of examination assessment methodology from PPT to electronic assessment, examination number generation approach has to transform requiring more efficient and effective algorithm to generate examination numbers in batches, provide authentication to examination numbers, assemble question papers automatically with the examination numbers and prevent collision.

A large body of literature exists in on-line examination systems mediated by cryptography for effective examination administration. Sarjius (2019) implemented an

independent CBT to introduce confidentiality, authenticity and integrity to examination administration through three cryptographic algorithms: encryption and decryption of examination questions, randomization of questions and authentication using fingerprint biometrics. Although simulation results indicated that it was scalable, flexible and capable of reducing impersonation and question leakage, it did not provide modalities for secure access of question papers by students and elimination of use of proxy. Jegatha *et al* (2019) experimented with an online examination system for secure distribution, collection of questions and answers by capitalizing on security objectives of cryptographic schemes such as mutual authentication, key exchange, and encryption and decryption with imposed security policies. Although, performance assessment validates a greater prospect in the use of the CBT system than PPT, however, success in question distribution relied on encryption and personal information system where the IP address of system server and personal information submitted by students were used for secure transmission of questions. Questions personalization requires extra effort and time. Xiaoling *et al* (2021) proposed a decentralized examination management system that utilizes a

combination of distributed storage system, block chain technology, facial recognition system and online educational platforms to introduce collusion resistance, dispute resolution, confidentiality, tamper resistance and access control to online examination system through the effectiveness of cryptographic primitives and fuzzy vaulting. However, it also uses biometric-personalized information for question distribution.

In this research, an ENGAS for CBT that caters for modern CBT administration requirements was proposed. This technique ensures that the examination numbers provided led to secure and automated question paper assembly. This was realized using cryptographic algorithms such as Elliptic Curve Cryptography and Digital Signature Schemes. The best-known encryption scheme based on elliptic curve cryptography is Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme (ECIES) (Shamsher *et al*, 2023; Chetan *et al*, 2022) It combines the properties of elliptic curve and discrete logarithm problem and finds wide application in light weight heterogeneous systems in internet of things, digital signature and key agreement (Salim and Amal, 2016). Digital signature is one of the cryptographic primitives used in the digital world to create a valid signature for the message to provide message integrity and non-repudiation (Chandrashekhara *et al*, 2021). The acceptance of these highlighted technologies was decided taking the following facts into consideration: The cryptographic algorithms used are in-line with IEEE standards. For examples, IEEE Standard 1363-2000 specifies ECC for Public Key Cryptographic Standard (PKCS) while IEEE Standard 1363a-2004 specifies DSA and undeniable signature for signature schemes.

METHODOLOGY

The ENGAS was designed primarily to provide secure and automatic assembly of available question papers produced by randomization. The rest of this section focuses on the following developmental approach to ENGAS: Preliminary investigation, Architecture, protocol for integrating ENGAS to CBT, design of ENGAS systems and implementation.

Preliminary Investigation

The requirements for the ENGAS were carried out using Knowledge Analysis of Tasks (KAS) and Joint Application

Design (JAD). During KAS, provisional security requirements for CBT were extracted from International Test Commission guidelines on test security and aggregated to form new requirements. During JAD, the aggregated requirements were jointly reviewed and contextualized through the instrumentation of a pilot study. This involved the generation of a questionnaire using the aggregated requirements as a knowledge structure that was administered to ICT Directors in some universities and CBT owners in Nigeria. Table 1 shows the contextualized requirements emerging from the pilot study:

Architecture of Examination Number Generation, Authentication and Inversion System

The architecture of ENGAS is shown in Figure 1: It comprises of the Provisional Question Paper System (PQPS), Examination Number Generation System (ENGS), Examination Number Inversion System (ENIS), Examination Number Authentication System (ENAS) and Software Automation System (SAS). The ENGS is responsible for generation of 92002 batches of examination numbers using the Congruence Generator (CG) and Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme (ECIES). The SAS comprises of the system's classes, Language Integrated Query and Entity Framework. It is responsible for all communication with the database including query generation, execution and generation of interfaces to display query results. The ENAS authenticates all examination numbers before inversion by ENIS to generate question paper for requesting students.

Design of the Examination Number Generation, Authentication and Inversion System

The ENGAS was compartmentalized into four systems: ENGS, ENAS, ENIS and PQPS. Therefore, the rest of this section focuses exclusively on the design of each subsystem to establish its functionalities.

Provisional Question Papers

The Provisional Question Papers were extracted from Cryptographic Security Scheme by (Fiemobebefa *et al*, 2024). It consists of one hundred and fifty distinct sequences indexed with seeds as summarized in Table 2.

Table 1: Contextualized Requirements and Proposed Technologies

Problem Gap	Proposed Technology	Problem Solved
There is need for key-based examination number generation system.	Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme	Generate examination numbers in batches for effective batch-based examination administration. Examination numbers must be mathematically linked to question papers for direct access and automated question paper generation.
There is need for key-based examination number authentication system	Chaum-Van Antwerpen Signature Scheme	Key-based examination number verification for secure access to question papers. This in combination with protocol helped to eliminate the use of proxy.

Figure 1: Architecture of Examination number Generation and Authentication Scheme

Table 2: Summary of Question Paper Extracted from Fiemobebefa *et al.* (2024)

$i/Seed, b$	7399, 3	7186, 7	3950, 11	5424, 15	318, 19	2724, 23	4435, 27	2611, 31	..	5637, 599
I	N_{i+1}		N_{i+1}							
0	46	47	42	19	33	29	20	35		35
1	35	42	31	10	23	16	8	51		51
2	2	27	51	45	35	18	51	39		14
3	9	35	5	44	18	24	21	42		30
4	30	6	26	41	20	42	37	51		46
5	40	25	36	32	26	43	32	25		9
6	17	29	13	5	44	46	17	0	..	25
7	1	41	50	30	45	2	25	31		41
8	6	24	2	52	48	29	49	18		4
9	21	26	17	12	4	4	15	32		20
10	13	32	9	51	31	35	19	21		36
11	42	50	38	9	6	22	31	41		52
12	23	51	19	42	37	36	14	48		15
13	19	1	15	35	24	25	16	26		31
14	7	10	3	14	38	45	22	16	..	47
15	24	37	20	4	27	52	40	3		10
16	22	12	18	27	47	20	41	40		26
17	16	43	12	43	1	30	44	45		42
18	51	30	47	38	22	7	0	7	..	5
19	50	44	46	23	32	44	27	52		21
:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:		:
47	12	46	8	36	41	19	46	13		45
48	39	39	35	17	36	27	6	17		8
49	14	18	10	13	21	51	45	29	...	24
50	45	8	41	1	29	17	3	12		40
51	32	31	28	18	0	21	36	14		3
52	25	23	21	19	17	15	13	11	..	19

Each sequence was obtained by random permutation using combined Pseudo-Random Number Generator and composite Linear Congruential Generator and represents a question paper.

Examination Number Generation System

The ENGS was designed to generate 92002 batches of examination numbers containing 600 examination numbers per batch. Each examination number provides access to the

provisional question papers. The stage-by-stage design approach for the ENGS includes: generation of 600 congruencies using CG, generation of keys using ECIES and encryption of congruencies to generate examination numbers.

Step 1: Generation of Six Hundred Congruences

According to Chistof and Jan (2010), the Congruences Generator is defined as following:

Table 3: Summary of Six Hundred Congruences for Examination Number Generation

J	Seeds	Congruences			
1	7399	15591	23783	31975	40167
2	7186	15378	23570	31762	39954
3	3950	12142	20334	28526	36718
4	5424	13616	21808	30000	38192
5	318	8510	16702	24894	33086
6	4435	12627	20819	29011	37203
7	2511	10703	18895	27087	35279
8	900	9092	17284	25476	33668
:	:	:	:	:	:
150	5637	13829	22021	30213	38405

Figure 2: Communication Protocol for Integrating the ENGAS to a CBT

$$C = S_n + KM \tag{1}$$

C = System of congruences, S = seeds from provisional data, M (modulus) = 8192, k (Multiplication factor) $\leq \frac{600}{150} = 4$.

Table 4: Encryption Points on the Elliptic Curve

Batches of Examination Numbers (w)	Encryption point $W\gamma\alpha$ mod 92003
1	47α
2	94α
3	141α
4	188α
5	235α
:	:
92001	91909
92002	91956 α

To generate the 600 congruences using the 150 seeds from Table 1, Equation 1 was used as follows: $S_1 = 7399$, taking $1 \leq k \leq 4$, the first four congruencies are: 15591, 23783, 31975 and 40167. Following this procedure, the rest were computed as summarized in Table 3.

Step 2: Generation of Keys

Based on (Chistof and Jan, 2010), the algorithm for ECIES for key generation is defined as follows:

$$y^2 = (x^3 + ax + c) \text{ Mod } P \tag{2}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P &\equiv 3 \text{ Mod } 4 \\ \text{or} \\ P - 3 &= n * 4 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3}$$

P is a prime modulus if and only if $k^P \text{ Mod } P = k$. The graph of elliptic curve described in Equation 2 is given in

Figure 3: Diagram of Elliptic Curve: $Y^2 = X^3 + 43X + 500$ over Real Number

Table 5: Double-And-Add Algorithm for Generating the Coordinates of 47α

Binary representation of 47		Current results
1	Initialize setting of $\alpha = (11, 48)$	(11, 48)
0	$\alpha + \alpha = 2\alpha$	(515, 43822)
1	$2\alpha + 2\alpha = 4\alpha$	(18744, 29406)
	$4\alpha + \alpha = 5\alpha$	(91110, 15027)
1	$5\alpha + 5\alpha = 10\alpha$	(59311, 81898)
	$10\alpha + \alpha = 11\alpha$	(85064, 41040)
1	$11\alpha + 11\alpha = 22\alpha$	(8503, 70634)
	$22\alpha + \alpha = 23\alpha$	(61626, 46778)
1	$23\alpha + 23\alpha = 46\alpha$	(37329, 69974)
	$46\alpha + \alpha = 47\alpha$	(37956, 57608)

Table 6: Evaluation of Exponentiation using Square-And-Multiply Algorithm

Binary Representation of exponent (92001)	Evaluation Process	Initial Values
1	Initialize base = 37956	37956
0	$37956^2 \text{ mod } 92003$	74962
1	$74962^2 \times 37956$	58286
1	$58286^2 \times 37956$	54882
0	54882^2	39710
0	39710^2	44683
1	$44683^2 \times 37956$	38450
1	$38450^2 \times 37956$	17320
1	$17320^2 \times 37956$	43596
0	43596^2	13242
1	$13242^2 \times 37956$	55632
1	$55632^2 \times 37956$	65937
0	65937^2	86204
0	86204^2	47306
0	47306^2	68667
0	68667^2	3139
1	$3139^2 \times 37956$	88864

Figure 3 characterized by the parameters generated as follows:

The primitive generator, $\alpha = (11, 48)$, $Z_p = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4 \dots 92002\}$, $a, b \in Z_p$, $a = 43$ and $b = 500$,

P (possible prime modulus) = 88003, 92003, 200003 and 44000003, $k =$ any random number.

$$\text{Encryption point} = \gamma w \alpha \text{ Mod } 92003 \tag{4}$$

$$2\alpha = \{(11, 48) + (11, 48): x_1 = x_2 = 11, y_1 = y_2 = 48 \text{ and } a = 43\}, M = 92003$$

Point Doubling for 2α (Double Function)

$$\lambda = (3x_1^2 + a) (2y_1)^{-1} \text{ Mod } P \tag{5}$$

Table 7: Key Parameters for the First Four Batch of Examination Numbers

Batches	Encryption point (x_0y_0)	Encryption Key (x_0)	Decryption key ($x_0^{-1} \text{ Mod } 92003$)	Batch Constant (y_0)
1	(37956, 57608)	37956	88864	57608
2	(58238, 28349)	58238	21872	28349
3	(47258, 15707)	47258	28410	15707
4	(78750, 86420)	78750	32225	86420

Figure 4: Communication Protocol for Chaum-Van Antwerpen Signature Scheme

$$x_3 = (\lambda^2 - 2x) \text{ Mod } P \quad (6)$$

$$y_3 = (\lambda(x - x_3) - y) \text{ Mod } P \quad (7)$$

$$3\alpha = \{(x_3, y_3) + (11, 48): x_1 = 1, y_1 = 48\} \text{Add Function}$$

$$\lambda = (y_3 - y_1)(x_3 - x_1)^{-1} \text{ Mod } P \quad (8)$$

$$x_4 = (\lambda^2 - x_1 - x_3) \text{ Mod } P \quad (9)$$

$$y_4 = (\lambda(x_1 - x_4) - y_1) \text{ Mod } P \quad (10)$$

$$a^p = a \text{ (Mod } p) \quad (11)$$

$$a^{p-2} = a^{-1} \text{ (Mod } p) \quad (12)$$

The 92002 encryption points on the elliptic curve for integer values of w are given in Table 4

Coordinates of encryption points with higher orders of α such as 47α were obtained from the coordinates of α and 2α using Equations 5 to 12 in the Double-And-Add algorithm shown in Table 5.

If the coordinates of the encryption point is (x_0, y_0) from double-And-Add algorithm, then:

$$\text{Encryption Key} = x_0, \text{ Batch Constant} = y_0.$$

$$\text{Decryption Key} = x_0^{-1} = x_0^{p-2} \text{ (Mod } P) \quad (13)$$

For the encryption point 47α with coordinates (37956, 57608), the decryption key was computed from Equation 14 as: $37956^{-1} \text{ Mod } 92003 = 37956^{92001} \text{ Mod } 92003 = 88864$

The evaluation of $37956^{92001} \text{ Mod } 92003$ was done using Square-And-Multiply algorithm as shown in Table 6. The decryption keys for 94α , 141α and 188α were obtained using similar approach. Table 7 shows summary of the first four key parameters for the ECIES.

Step 3: Generation of Examination Numbers by Encryption

$$e_k(C + y_0, k) = E = x_0 * (C + y_0) \text{ Mod } P \quad (14)$$

To generate the first batch of examination numbers, where: $w = 1, x_0 = 37956, y_0 = 57608$, Equation 13 was used to encrypt the congruence in Table 3 as follows:

$$E_1 = (15591 + 57608) \times 37956 \text{ Mod } 92003 = 34650,$$

$$E_2 = (23783 + 57608) \times 37956 \text{ Mod } 92003 = 62,$$

$$E_4 = (40167 + 57608) \times 37956 \text{ Mod } 92003 = 22889.$$

Table 8 shows the first batch of examination numbers. Similar approach was used for other batches.

Table 8: Summary of the First Batch of Examination Numbers

S/N	Examination Numbers			
1	34650	62	57477	22889
2	46286	11698	69113	34525
3	44675	10087	92087	32914
4	53995	76773	76822	42234
.				
.				
149	42359	7771	65186	30598
150	27764	85179	50591	16003

Examination Number Authentication System

The ENAS was designed using Chaum-Van Antwerpen Signature Scheme (CASS). It is an undeniable signature scheme where the signature cannot be verified without the cooperation of the signer. This novel feature of CASS was capitalized on to provide key-based examination number authentication. Therefore, the design of CASS for key-based examination number verification requires two steps:

Mathematical framework with Parameter generation and communication protocol for CASS.

Stage 1: Mathematical Framework with Parameter Generation

According to Atul and Indivar (2020), the CASS without disavowal protocol is defined as follows: for the set of keys K provided in Equation 15, for the scheme, the signing algorithm is as follows:

$$K = \{(P, \alpha, \gamma, \beta) : \beta \equiv \alpha^\gamma \text{ Mod } P\} \quad (15)$$

$$x = E^2 \text{ Mod } P \quad (16)$$

$$P = 2q + 1 \quad (18)$$

$$c = y^{e1} \beta^{e2} \text{ mod } P \quad (19)$$

$$d_1 = c^{\gamma^{-1} \text{ mod } q} \text{ mod } P \quad (20)$$

$$T_1 = (d_1 || \beta || \gamma || E) \quad (21)$$

The verification algorithm is given as follows:

$$d_2 = x^{e1} \alpha^{e2} \text{ Mod } P \quad (22)$$

$$T_2 = (d_2 || \beta || \gamma || E) \quad (23)$$

The examination number E is authentic if and only if: $T_1 = T_2$ (24)

Table 9: Algorithm for Examination Number Generation System

Algorithm 1: Double-And-Add Function (w)

1	currentResult_x ← 11; currentResult_y ← 48; batchNum ← w;	23	End
2	encryptPoint ← batchNum * 47;	24	while (Arr.Count > 0)
3	while (encryptPoint > 0)	25	Begin
4	Begin	26	if (val == 1 && i == 0)
5	Arr ← (encryptPoint % 2);	27	Begin
6	encryptPoint ← encryptPoint / 2;	28	new_x ← 11;
7	new_y ← 48;	29	i++
8	End	30	End
9	if (val == 1 && i != 0)	31	encryptor ← currentResult_x;
10	Begin	32	batchConstant ← currentResult_y;
11	Result ← DoubleFuntion (new_x, new_y);	33	decryptor ← MultiplicativeInverseModuloN(encryptor, 92003);
12	currentResult_y ← Result.Pop ();	34	SaveKeys (w, encryptor, decryptor and batchConstant);
13	currentResult_x ← Result.Pop ();	35	foreach (long seed in QuestionType)
14	Result ← AddFunction(currentResult_x, currentResult_y);	36	Begin
15	currentResult_y ← Result.Pop ();	37	for (x = 1; x <= 4; x++)
16	currentResult_x ← Result.Pop ();	38	Begin
17	End	39	congruence ← seed + x * 8192;
18	if (val == 0 && i != 0)	40	ComputeValueExamNo =
19	Begin	41	(encryptor * (congruence + batchConstant)) % 92003;
20	Result ← DoubleFuntion (new_x, new_y);	42	StudentExamNo ← w_ComputeValueExamNo;
21	currentResult_y ← Result.Pop ();	43	End
22	currentResult_x ← Result.Pop ();	44	Return StudentExamNo;
23	End	45	End

The parameters for the CASS are follows:

$$P = 44,000,003. q = 22,000,001, Z_p = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 44000003\}, Z_p^* = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 44000003\}.$$

The cardinality of $|Z_p^*| = 44000002 = 1 \times 2 \times 22000001$.

The subgroup Z_p^* with cardinality of 22000001: $(H_4) = \{1, 4, 16, 64, 256, 1024, 4096, 16384, 65536, 262144, 1048576, 4194304, 16777216, 23108861\}$, $\alpha = 4096$ (primitive generator of H_4), $e_1 = 25$ and $e_2 = 49 \in Z_q$, γ (Private key) = password, E = Examination Number,

Stage 2: Communication Protocol for the Chaum-Van Antwerpen Signature Scheme

The communication protocol for the CASS is shown in Figure 4. It has two parts: Signature generation and verification. The protocol is elaborated in steps as follows:

Step 1: to begin with, during signature generation, the composite signature tag T_2 and public key β were generated using Equation 15, 22 and 23 using the examination number and password as inputs.

Step 2: next, the composite signature tag and public key were stored in the database for cross referencing and re-use respectively.

Step 3: during verification, the public key was first extracted as part of the profile information during biometric verification and retained by the proctor after student identification.

Step 4: the proctor supplied the verification key to aid the student login on the interface together with the examination number.

Step 5: the ENGAS computed T_1 using Equations 15 to 21 compared with T_2 as template. If a match was found, ENIS was invoked to generate the question papers for student to start exam

Examination Number Inversion System

After successful authentication, the examination numbers were inverted to generate the question paper. The examination number inversion process requires two steps: the ECIES decryption function and direct modular reduction and question paper generation.

$$C = ((E * x_0^{-1}) - y_0) \text{ Mod } P \tag{25}$$

$$S_n = C \text{ mod } M \tag{26}$$

Where: M = 8192, the decryption key and batch constant for Equation 24 are given in Table 6.

SOFTWARE AUTOMATION SYSTEM

The SAS comprises of the ENGAS classes, Language Integrated query, Entity Framework and database Management System. It uses the seed, S_n to identify the sequence defined in Table 2, encapsulate the sequence in a correlated sub-query, execute the query and generate the exact question paper corresponding to the sequence.

Table 10: Algorithm for Examination Number Authentication and InversionChaum-VanGeneration (BatchNum, Password, E)

46	Begin	52	$Ver \leftarrow (Ver1 * Ver2) \% P;$
47	$w_1 \leftarrow \text{BatchNum}; E \leftarrow \text{ExamNum}; \gamma \leftarrow \text{password};$	53	$\text{discretLog} = \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(\alpha, \gamma, P);$
48	$\alpha \leftarrow 4096; e_1 \leftarrow 25; e_2 \leftarrow 49; P \leftarrow 44000003; q \leftarrow 22000001;$	54	$T2 \leftarrow (Ver \text{discretLog} \gamma E);$
49	$X_1 \leftarrow (E^2) \% P;$	55	Return T2, discretLog;
50	$Ver1 \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(X_1, e_1, P);$	56	End
51	$Ver2 \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(\alpha, e_2, P);$	57	
Chaum-VanVerification (BatchNum, password, E)			
58	Begin	66	$C \leftarrow (C_1 * C_2) \% P;$
59	$w_1 \leftarrow \text{BatchNum}; X \leftarrow \text{ExamNum}; \gamma \leftarrow \text{password};$	67	$\gamma^{-1} \leftarrow \text{MultiplicativeInverseModuloN}(\gamma, q);$
60	$\alpha \leftarrow 4096; e_1 \leftarrow 25; e_2 \leftarrow 49; P \leftarrow 44000003; q \leftarrow 22000001;$	68	$d_1 \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(C, \gamma^{-1}, P);$
61	$X_1 \leftarrow (E^2) \% P;$	69	$T_1 \leftarrow d_1 \text{VerificationKey} \gamma E ;$
62	$\text{VerificationKey} \leftarrow \text{discretLog};$	70	if ($T_1 = T_2$)
63	$Y \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(X_1, \gamma, P);$	71	Begin
64	$C_1 \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(Y, e_1, P);$	72	Questions $\leftarrow \text{ExaminationNumberInversion}(w_1, X, \gamma);$
65	$C_2 \leftarrow \text{ExponentiationModuloP}(\text{VerificationKey}, e_2, P);$	73	End
ExaminationNumberInversion (w_1, X, γ)			
75	Begin	74	End
76	$\text{ExamNum} \leftarrow X; \text{batchNum} \leftarrow w_1; \text{Password} \leftarrow \gamma;$	81	$\text{Congruence} = ((\text{decryptor} * \text{ExamNum}) - (\text{batchConstant})) \% 92003;$
77	if ($\text{batchNum} = w_1$ and $\text{ExamNum} == X$)	82	$\text{Seed} \leftarrow \text{Congruence} \% 8192;$
78	Begin	83	$\text{Signature} \leftarrow \text{DSASignInFunction}(\text{seed}, \text{password});$
79	Get decryptor, batchConstant	84	$\text{StudentQuestion} \leftarrow \text{GenerateQuestionType}(\text{seed});$
80	End;	85	Return StudentQuestion;
		86	End;

Figure 5: Output of ENGS: Section of First Batch of Examination Numbers and Keys

Figure 6: Output of ENGS: Section of Second Batch of Examination Numbers and Keys

Figure 7: Output of ENGS: Section of Third Batch of Examination Numbers and Keys

High-Level Algorithm for Examination Number Generation, Authentication and Inversion Subsystem

The high-level algorithm for ENGAS requires three separate algorithms as shown in Tables 9 and 10, Add-And-Double algorithm to implement examination number generation, CASS algorithm to implement authentication and separate algorithm for inversion. Therefore, the Greedy Algorithm development approach was adopted to develop the algorithm part by part. The Add-And-Double algorithm utilizes point addition and point doubling to

implement Point Multiplication. Therefore, the Recursive Algorithm development approach was also adopted where separate algorithms were built for Add-Function and Double-Function to be called when required into Add-And-Double algorithm for point multiplication. Also, the sub-parts such as Add Function require the computation of multiplicative inverse and modular exponentiation. Therefore, the formula was split into smaller units and the Divide-And-Conquer Algorithm was adopted also to build the algorithm for the inverse and exponentiation. Finally, the outputs were merged with the remaining solution to get a final solution

Figure 8: Admin Interface for Creating Exam Numbers in Batches.

Figure 9: First Batch of Examination Numbers and Keys in the CBT

Figure 10: First Section of Questions in the Database

Implementation and Testing

Implementation of ENGAS involves simulation of the developed algorithm to ascertain that they were correctly written, integration of ENGAS into a CBT and testing.

During simulation, well defined classes were first written for the ENGAS algorithms using standard C# code. Each class encapsulated methods and variables that represented the cryptographic functions that were re-used extensively. The classes were then configured on a visual studio integrated development environment and the parameterized methods under each class were called and ran under the main's method with known inputs. Since each class created represented a self-contained unit, then the

methods were accurately tested in isolation using this process. It was verified that the outputs of the various mathematical operations were as expected. This implies that if the algorithms are used in a more complex CBT application, the verified functionalities of each class would remain in a working state and perform as designed. Next, ENGAS was integrated to a CBT using ASP.NET CORE, Entity Framework and SQL Server 2014 database. The developmental approach used with Entity Framework Core for this application was the Code-First Approach. Therefore, the Controller, Model and View Classes were configured on the main CBT first and ran. Finally, coverage testing was conducted to ascertain the completeness, accuracy and consistency of the ENGAS immediately after development. The testing strategy involved conducting

Figure 11: Student’s Interface Requiring Verification Key for Examination Number Authentication

Figure 12: Question Paper Generated after Examination Number Authentication

Table 11: Security Function Distribution

S/N	ENGAS Systems	Cryptography Algorithms	Description	Security Function
1	Provisional Question Paper Generation System	Not required in ENGAS. It is in the referenced paper	This feature generated 150 seeds which were used for indexing each question paper.	Non
2	Examination Number Generation System	Congruence Generator	This algorithm was used to generate 600 congruences from the 140 seeds. These congruences were encrypted repeatedly to generate the batches of examination numbers	600
		Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme	This algorithm was used to generate 92002 batches of examination numbers and keys. For each set of key consisting of encryptor, decryptor and batch constant, one batch of examination was created.	92002
3	Examination Number Authentication System	Chaum-Van Antwerpen Signature Scheme	This cryptographic algorithm was used to authentication each examination number imputed by a student with the aid of a verification key by generating and comparing signature tags.	1
4	Examination Number Inversion System	ECIES Decryption Function	Decryption of examination numbers to congruences	1
		Inverse Congruence Generator	Direct modular reduction of congruences to seeds	1

performance testing by ensuring that all the interfaces were generated as required. Additionally, the end-to-end cryptographic functions such as generation of examination numbers and keys in batches and authentication were tested as required for usability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section data obtained during simulation of ENGAS classes and integration of ENGAS to CBT were presented. Also, analysis involving determination of security level was

provided. This information forms the basis for discussion and recommendations.

Results of Simulation and Integration

The simulation was focused majorly on the generation of examination numbers. About 92002 batches of examination numbers were generated by simply passing the batch numbers which ranged from 1 to 92002. Each batch of examination numbers comprises of the examination numbers, encryption key, decryption key and batch constant. Figures 7 to 8 gives the results.

During integration and coverage testing, a number of main control interfaces and subordinate interfaces were generated to allow providing access to all parts of the CBT and interactivity. In this section, these interfaces were provided in Figure 8 to 12 as evidence of data flow.

Determination of Security Level of the Scheme

Security level is degree of peakedness of the security functions contributed by the cryptographic features in ENGAS when compared with a normal distribution. Two steps were taken to determine the security level of ENGAS: Determination of security function distribution and computation of the security level using moment coefficient of kurtosis.

Step 1: Determination of Security Function Distribution

application is leptokurtic. It is more peaked than platykurtic and mesokurtic distribution indicating that the ENGAS is perfectly consolidated with adequate security features for automatic question paper assembly.

Discussion

The ENGAS was successfully developed and implemented with three systems mediated by cryptography: ENGS, ENIS and ENAS. Results of simulation of the developed algorithms for accuracy followed by integration to CBT indicated that the ENGAS performed the desired functions. These are the generation of 92002 batches of examination numbers and keys, real time key-based authentication of the generated examination numbers which led to the examination number inversion and automated assembly of the question papers without personalizing question papers for each student using his/

Table 12: Computation Security Level using Moment Coefficient of Kurtosis

Security Function Distribution (x)	Frequency of points (f)	Mean (\bar{x})	$f(x - \bar{x})^2$	$f(x - \bar{x})^4$
600	1	18521	321162241	103145185044142081
92002	1	18521	5399457361	29154139793257084321
1	3	18521	1028971200	352927243476480000
	$\sum f=5$		$\sum f(x - \bar{x})^2 = 6749590802$	$\sum f(x - \bar{x})^4 = 29610212221777706402$
$m_2 = \frac{6749590802}{5} = 1349918160.4$		$m_4 = \frac{29610212221777706402}{5} = 592204244435541280.4$		

Therefore, the moment coefficient of Kurtosis about the mean = $\frac{592204244435541280.4}{1349918160.4^2} = 3.25$

Security function distribution is the number of functions which each cryptographic feature contributed to the security of the ENGAS. Table 11 shows the cryptographic features, descriptions and security functions.

Step 2: Computation of Security Level

Computation of the security level was done using moment coefficient of kurtosis as shown in Table 12. According to (Christiana *et al*, 2023), the various related mathematical formulas are as follows

$$\text{Moment coefficient of Kurtosis} = \frac{m_4}{m_2^2} \tag{27}$$

$$m_4 = \frac{(X_1-A)^4 + (X_2-A)^4 + (X_3-A)^4 + \dots + (X_n-A)^4}{n} \tag{28}$$

$$m_2 = M_2 = \frac{(X_1-A)^2 + (X_2-A)^2 + (X_3-A)^2 + \dots + (X_n-A)^2}{n} \tag{29}$$

$\frac{m_4}{m_2^2} = 3$ for normal, $\frac{m_4}{m_2^2} > 3$ for leptokurtic and $\frac{m_4}{m_2^2} < 3$ for platykurtic distribution

Where: m_2 = second moment about the mean, m_4 = fourth moment about the mean, n = number of observations, A= mean.

The moment coefficient of kurtosis is 3.25 which is more than 3. The distribution of security functions in this

her personal information and IP address of the computers. This reduced time, effort and completely eased out examination administration processes. Also, in administering ENGAS-enhanced CBT which has prefixed biometric verification system, user profile containing identification information of each student such as the verification key and passport was generated immediately after biometric verification. The verification key was not exposed to the student but kept by proctor verifying the student and supplied to help each student to log in. This procedure helped to eliminate the use of proxy. A proxy is another more competent student who has no stake in the examination but gets paid to register and help the student to pass examination. A necessary strategy used by a student and his/her proxy in CBT is to exchange information such as examination numbers, password and registration numbers to login and take examination in his/her behalf.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Potentially, the inclusion of ENGAS to CBT will offer many security services to examination administration. Firstly, it provides a wider scope to accommodate more students particularly in national examinations. 92002

examination centers each with a capacity of 600 students are possible (total of over 55 million examination numbers). At each center, each of the 600 examination numbers securely provides access to the available 150 question papers generated by randomization. Secondly, it provides enhanced security due to the elimination of use of proxy and other avenues to harvesting questions. Finally, ENGAS is very scalable and capable of meeting increasing population demand. For extreme population increase beyond the capability of 92002 batches (over 55 million examination numbers), ENGAS can ultimately be reconfigured to new prime modulus, $P = 200003$ or 44000003 providing 200002 batches (over 120 million) or 44000002 batches (over 25 billion examination numbers) to meet the demand. In general, it imparts holistic examination administration. However, it is worthwhile to suggest that the elimination of use of proxy as an improvement to CBT security can only be achieved by integrating ENGAS to CBT with prefixed biometric verification system for mitigation of impersonation, otherwise, the proxy can successfully impersonate. Another security measure recommended is incorporation of sign-in and sign-out security system to provide non-repudiation of student participation in examination.

POTENTIAL FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

Nigerian Education System started standardization testing in 1978. This depended on randomization, examination number system and attendance management with paper and Pen for security. With the adoption of CBT particularly into Nigeria, research direction involves maximizing these three areas in software form to improve validity and credibility in CBT assessment. The use of digital attendance management system for comprehensive user authentication for instance should have multi-layer, multifactor authentication: The first layer for mitigation of impersonation, second layer for mitigation of use of proxy and third layer for introduction of non-repudiation. Cryptographic algorithms are well suited for this purpose with multiple input capabilities and can be compounded in layer as required. Therefore, the development of ENGAS for mitigation of use of proxy was not incidental. Additionally, it can be used as part of an Electronic Voting System in combination with biometric for a double layer authentication system. During registration, electorate could be given a code (instead of examination number) after biometric for supervised voting during verification with keys. Good enough, both CBT and voting systems use different events such as registration, verification etc. Event flow strategy could utilize biometric, ENGAS and sign-in and sign-out layers differently to avoid bottle necking or congestions.

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